

Université Libanaise

LEBANESE UNIVERSITY
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
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Master 2 Specialized Project Report

Civil Engineering – Option Petroleum Structures (Ch. E)

2018-2019

**Degradation of Toxic Microplastics in the Lebanese Water
by Developing and Applying an Innovative Photocatalytic Method**

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Acknowledgements

As a start, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my thesis supervisor Prof. Wael Hamd for his invaluable expertise in the research topic and work methodology. His continuous support, encouragement and counseling cleared the way for me to be able to work on my own under the shadow of his knowledge.

I would like to thank Dr. Rami Nader and Dr. Jean Chamoun for agreeing to be part of the jury who would be judging my work. Their valuable comments on my work will be a foundation for my work in the future.

I would also like to express my endless appreciation to my parents and to my partner for their irreplaceable support and inspiration during this thesis. Thank you for everything you have done to allow this achievement to happen. Your presence in my life is something I will always cherish.

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Summary

The increasing rate of toxic microplastics in water forms a threat to human health through the food chain and causes serious ecological problems. Several treatment techniques such as incineration, filtration and chlorination require a large consumption of energy. The use of photocatalytic techniques based on the advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) emerges as an innovative, environmentally friendly, inexpensive and efficient method for treatment. ZnO nanorods (ZnO NRs) semiconductor photocatalyst synthesized by hydrothermal growth on glass fiber substrates is recognized to be an ideal candidate to absorb sunlight and to perform the photocatalytic degradation of pollutants and microplastics. The main goal of this research is to optimize the kinetic degradation of microplastics into non-harmful molecules such as CO₂ and H₂O.

For the purpose of this research, photocatalyst synthesis was first done on glass substrate using hydrothermal growth, to ensure the growth of ZnO classical organic molecule on a glass substrate. The success of this step allowed us to pursue our target in applying the technique of growth of ZnO nanorods on glass fiber substrate. The need for glass fiber as a substrate arises from the fact that microplastics have a lower density than water, which makes them float at the surface, thus not allowing them to contact a classical glass substrate. Accordingly, trapping technique was used to trap the microplastics in the glass fibers. SEM spectroscopy results showed neatly distributed nanorods of ZnO grown on fiber glass substrate. The photocatalysis process was applied for a total of 196 hours under natural sunlight, and the degradation was studied using FTIR-ATR spectroscopy. After the oxidation of polypropylene, new characteristic peaks were viewed in the oxidized polymer: carbonyl group in the range of absorbance values 1700 cm⁻¹ to 1780 cm⁻¹, OH stretching peaks were formed and seen at 3400 cm⁻¹, and unsaturated carbon bonds were detected by the evolution of the peaks at 868 cm⁻¹. To properly assess the degradation rate of polypropylene, the CI over several times of the samples taken, and the results showed a final CI value around 6 times higher than the original one. Considering the size of the polypropylene particles used which was 300 μm, and the time spent under sunlight, this CI value is a promising one as it can be highly increased while increasing the time of degradation.

Keywords: Photocatalytic degradation – Zinc oxide nanorods – Polypropylene – Microplastics – Sunlight

Résumé

L'augmentation du taux de microplastiques toxiques dans l'eau constitue une menace pour la santé humaine dans la chaîne alimentaire et cause de graves problèmes écologiques. Plusieurs techniques de traitement, telles que l'incinération, la filtration et la chloration, nécessitent une consommation d'énergie importante. L'utilisation de techniques photocatalytiques basées sur les procédés d'oxydation avancés apparaît comme une méthode de traitement innovante, respectueuse de l'environnement, peu coûteuse et efficace. Le photocatalyseur semi-conducteur à base de nanorodes de ZnO (ZnO NRs) synthétisé par croissance hydrothermale sur des substrats en fibre de verre est reconnu comme étant le candidat idéal pour absorber la lumière solaire et effectuer la dégradation photocatalytique des polluants et des microplastiques. L'objectif principal de cette recherche est d'optimiser la dégradation cinétique des microplastiques en molécules non nocives telles que CO₂ et H₂O.

Aux fins de cette recherche, la synthèse de photocatalyseur a d'abord été effectuée sur un substrat de verre en utilisant une croissance hydrothermale, afin d'assurer la croissance de la molécule organique classique de ZnO sur un substrat de verre. Le succès de cette étape nous a permis de poursuivre notre objectif en appliquant la technique de croissance de nanorodes de ZnO sur un substrat en fibre de verre. La nécessité de la fibre de verre en tant que substrat provient du fait que les microplastiques ont une densité inférieure à celle de l'eau, ce qui les fait flotter à la surface, ce qui ne leur permet pas d'entrer en contact avec un substrat en verre classique. En conséquence, une technique de piégeage a été utilisée pour piéger les microplastiques dans les fibres de verre. Les résultats de la spectroscopie SEM ont montré des nanorodes de ZnO bien réparties sur un substrat de fibre de verre bien réparties. Le processus de photocatalyse a été appliqué pendant un total de 196 heures sous la lumière naturelle du soleil, et la dégradation a été étudiée par spectroscopie FTIR-ATR. Après l'oxydation du polypropylène, de nouveaux pics caractéristiques ont été observés dans le polymère oxydé: groupe carbonyle dans l'intervalle des valeurs d'absorbance 1700 cm⁻¹ à 1780 cm⁻¹, des pics d'étirement OH ont été observés à 3400 cm⁻¹ et du carbone non saturé. Les liaisons ont été détectées par l'évolution des pics à 868 cm⁻¹. Pour évaluer correctement le taux de dégradation du polypropylène, l'IC sur plusieurs fois des échantillons prélevés, les résultats ont montré une valeur finale d'IC environ 6 fois plus élevée que celle d'origine. Compte tenu de la taille des particules de polypropylène utilisées, qui était de 300 µm, et du temps passé au soleil, cette valeur de CI est prometteuse car elle peut être fortement augmentée tout en augmentant le temps de dégradation.

Mots-clés: Dégradation photocatalytique – Nanorodes d'oxyde de zinc – Polypropylène – Microplastiques – Lumière du soleil

List of Abbreviations

μm : Micrometer

ATR: Attenuated Total Reflectance

C: Concentration

CI: Carbonyl index

e^- : Electron

eV: Electron Volt

FTIR: Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

g: Gram

h^+ : Hole

m: Mass

meV: Millielectron Volt

ml: Milli liter

mM: Milli Molar

MW: Molecular weight

O_2^- : Superoxide anion

OH^* : Hydroxyl radical

PP: Polypropylene

SEM: Scanning Electron Microscopy

SI: International system of units

uv: Ultra-violet

V: Volume

ZnO: Zinc Oxide

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Introduction

In the past 50 years, the global plastic production has amplified by around 20 times, an amount that sums up to reach approximately 300 million tons per year (Gourmelon, 2017). These amounts include mostly packaging needs which are usually used only once and then disposed, in addition to other forms where plastic is used and then disposed of. This fact has led to the accumulation of plastic litter in the seas all over the world. Huge attention has been focused in the last decade over the abundance of plastics in water. Until 2014 only, a study by Eriksen et al. (2014) has reported that more than 92% of the plastics present in the seas are classified as microplastics because of their small size. Microplastics in water are considered a huge danger to humans and to the environment as well. Their infinitesimal size makes them available to marine animals, thus entering the food chain, reaching finally to humans. Ingestion of such molecules can cause cancerous diseases and can even be lethal at times. Thus, the presence of plastics and microplastics in the seas all over the world has urged researchers to find solutions to turn these particles into non-harmful molecules.

Although the demand for oil and gas is expected to decrease by 2050 due to the emerging sustainable technologies such as electric vehicles, the demand for petrochemical products such as plastics is projected to increase (Ghaddar & Bousoo, 2018). Oil rich countries in the Middle East are spending on new petrochemical plants due to the expected increase in demand. However, with plastics' reputation as one of the major pollutants that contaminate the oceans and harm the ecosystem, major oil and gas companies are investing in environmental research in order to clean up contaminated oceans. Eni has developed one of the recent technologies by the name of the Clean Sea robot (Eni, 2017). The project consists of an autonomous underwater vehicle that monitors and tracks the water quality. The exploration of a new technique to clean up water from microplastics, which are small-sized plastic particles, will come of a huge benefit to the oil and gas companies who are accused of contaminating the world's waters with the microplastics. This work will develop a new method for cleaning up microplastics from water by utilizing effective new methods.

This research aims to develop an environmentally friendly and cost-efficient technology, which is photocatalysis, for the removal of dangerous microplastics from Lebanese Sea water. This technology stands out amongst other methods mainly because it utilizes sunlight to break down these toxic molecules into nonharmful ones, for human health and for the environment as well. The scope of this work includes a thorough literature review for an understanding of what microplastics are, what are the dangers they provoke, and what are the existing methods to degrade them. A review on photocatalysis will also be

presented for a detailed understanding of the process. After the review, the laboratory work that was done will be presented in-depth, where the synthesis of zinc oxide nanorods on glass fiber substrate was obtained, to be used as a photocatalyst. Then, photocatalysis process that was done at the lab scale will be shown and the degradation results will be presented, analyzed and discussed. A brief conclusion and some future perspective will be finally given.

CLAIM Project

The “Cleaning Litter by Developing and Applying Innovative Methods in European Seas” project, which is also known as CLAIM, is a project that focuses on cleaning visible and invisible plastic particles from the Mediterranean and Baltic seas, as mentioned on their official website. The project involves two main stages. The first is developing a photocatalytic method of nanocoating in order to treat waters that are contaminated with microplastics. The second idea is to create new energy harvesting devices that utilize the solid waste products found in water in order to generate useful energy at ports. The methods of waste treatment that are being developed at CLAIM focus on tackling the waste issue at the river mouths and in the wastewater, treatment lines. The project takes into account several factors such as cost efficiency and the environmental impact of the proposed technologies. The ecosystem is also taken into account when considering the new devices or methods of treatment that will be implemented (Grant et al., 2012).

CLAIM was launched in November 1st of the year 2017 and will continue until the 31st of October of the year 2021 and has an overall budget of € 6,185,612.75. The program is coordinated by the Hellenic Center for Marine Research in Greece, with 19 partners coming from 14 different countries, as published officially by their website. Prof. Wael Hamd is the scientific leader of this project in Lebanon, and this research serves as part of the contribution of the Lebanese University in the project CLAIM.

Chapter 1: A Review on Microplastics

Microplastics are wastes constituted mainly of plastic that are found at a microscopic scale in water. These microplastics are found in almost all water sources in earth such as oceans, rivers and even ice caps. In order to be classified as microplastics, the particles should not exceed 1mm in length, and there is no lower size limit for those particles (Galloway & Lewis, 2016).

These microscopic plastic particles form because of the disintegration of larger plastic objects due to forces of nature such as wind and waves. Another source of disintegration is sunlight-induced photo-oxidation. This process occurs when the sun creates a reaction in hydrocarbons in which carbon and oxygen combine to form a new material that is soluble in water (Fingas, 2011). Moreover, small sized additives that are used in cosmetics and beauty products are one of the main sources of microplastics. This chapter introduces the main source of plastics which is the oil and gas industry. It also presents a definition for microplastics as has been used in research, their types, along with the sources from where microplastics might come. Finally, the chapter presents some traditional techniques that have been used for treatment of water from microplastics.

Types of Microplastics

The types of microplastics that are currently found in water around the world are divided into two main categories, primary and secondary microplastics that are characterized as follows (Boucher & Friot, 2017):

- **Primary Microplastics:** are small sized plastic particles that are used in cosmetics as mentioned above and remains of manufacturing facilities that are small. Another source of small plastic particles is from the contact between vehicle tires and the surface of the road that leads to the release of microplastics.
- **Secondary Microplastics:** are due to the disintegration of large plastic particles caused by natural phenomena. The objects that are disintegrated are often due to human activities such as using plastic bags.

There is a debate whether the main source of microplastics in the primary or secondary source. The discovery of large amounts of microplastics in lakes and rivers inside Europe indicates that the primary sources of microplastics make a large quantity of the microplastics found in water (Boucher & Friot, 2017). These particles come in different shapes and sizes that differ in their chemical structure. The density of those polymers determines their location in the water. Less dense polymer such as polyethylene

have a low density and thus float on the surface of water, while polymers with a density lower than that of water such as polyvinylchloride gather inside deep water (Galloway & Lewis, 2016).

Sources of Microplastics

According to Boucher (2017), the sources of microplastics found in the world's waters are classified as intentional and unintentional. Products that are intentionally put by humans into the water are classified as intentional sources, while other sources that release microplastics into the water such as accidental oil spills or tire debris are known as unintentional sources.

One of the main sources of microplastics are the plastic pellets that are used in order to create the plastic products that are used daily. These plastic pellets are small in size since they come in the form of powder or small sized particles (2 to 5 millimeters) (Duxbury, 1992). The manufacturing processes that involve these pellets often result in waste products that end up in seawater and oceans in the form of microplastics. This type of waste is classified as unintentional since humans don't place the plastic waste in water on purpose. Synthetic textiles are another source of microplastics that is abundant in the world's oceans. The process of washing clothes and textiles that leads to the shedding of fabric particles into sewage water that ends up in the oceans (Boucher, 2017). Large quantities of microplastics that are found in oceans are believed to originate from car tires (Wagner et al., 2018). The friction that takes place between the tires and the surface of the roads leads to the erosion of the materials that are found in car tires such as synthetic polymers and rubber. The material that is shed from tires is then carried out by the wind or by rainwater, which carries the microplastics into seas and oceans. Another source of microplastics that originates from the transportation industry are the road markings. Several synthetic materials are used in order to mark several signs and symbols on the roads. These markings are usually made using paint or thermoplastic materials (White, 1991). The weather conditions and tire interaction lead to the abrasion of those markings in the form of microplastics. Figure 1 sums up most of the major sources of microplastics.

Figure 1 Sources of microplastics (Dris et al., 2016)

One of the causes of formation of microplastics in seawater is the ship coatings. Most ships that sail in seawater are protected from corrosion and other natural effects. These coating contain several types of plastic based materials such as polyurethane and lacquers. This method of releasing microplastics into the sea is considered unintentional. One of the sources that is considered to be an intentional source of placing microplastics in water is the use of personal care products. Several care products and cosmetics contain a large quantity of microplastics in order to add structure to the products such as lipstick (Leslie, 2014). Even the packaging of these products is made out of plastic, which contributes in the process of increasing the microplastics in water around the world. The use of these personal care products is considered an intentional source of microplastics since the person using these products in intentionally placing it in the wastewater that ends up in the sea.

Table 1: World Plastic Consumption Per Year for Each Source (Boucher & Friot, 2017)

Sources	World Consumption (KTons/ Year of Plastic)	Intentional Loss	References
Synthetic Textiles	588,000	No	World Apparel Coalition (2011)
Plastic Pellets	257,000	No	Plastics Europe (2007)
Tires	6,431	No	ETRma (2010)
Road Markings	588	No	Grand View Research, Inc. (2016)
Marine Coatings	452	No	Coatings World (2012)
Personal Care Products	42	Yes	Leslie, H.A. (2015)

Table 1 summarizes the sources of plastic waste while classifying the intentional and unintentional sources. The major source of plastic is synthetic textiles, which records 588,000 kilotons per year according to World Apparel Coalition (2011). The Plastic Pellets that are used in the manufacturing of several plastic products is the second major source of plastic at 257,000 kilotons per year.

Presence in the Mediterranean Sea

The amount of microplastics in a sea is highly related to the population that surrounds it, at the coasts specifically. Considering the large population settling at the coasts of the Mediterranean Sea, that sum up to approximately 466 million people, it can be said that the bounded area of the Mediterranean basin is under a high demographic burden (UNEP/MAP, 2012). It is worth mentioning that the lack of outflow of water at the surface of the Mediterranean Sea is a reason for the accumulation of the pollutants in it. In addition, the existence of excessive activities ranging from fishing to touristic and manufacturing events as well, explains the high amounts of microplastics as compared to other seas. The presence of plastics in the sea is dangerous for humans, as well as the marine environment and marine animals. However, microplastics are much more hazardous. The concentration of microplastics in the Mediterranean Sea has been estimated to be 1.25 million fragments per km² (Kedzierski et al., 2019). This amount is around four times larger than the quantity of plastics in the “plastic island” in the North Pacific Ocean. The distribution of the sizes of plastic particles in the Mediterranean Sea is shown in the graph in figure 2. Most of the particles present are smaller than 5 mm in size, which classifies them as microplastics. Considering the dangers of microplastics presence in the seas, research is focusing high attention on technologies for the removal of these particles from water.

Figure 2 Particle size distribution in Mediterranean Sea (Suaria et al., 2016)

During the Ocean Conference held by the UN in 2017, an amount of plastics equivalent to 8 million tons has been reported to be thrown into the oceans every year. This amount makes up to 80% of all the garbage thrown to the seas. As a result of this, it is expected that most of the animals in the polluted seas intake microplastics in dangerous amounts. Figure 3 presents a sample of the turtles which die due to this fact.

Figure 3 Turtles dead due to microplastics' intake

The amounts of microplastics in water can be divided into several types. According to the research done by the Consolidated Research Group on Marine Geosciences of the Faculty of Earth Sciences at the University of Barcelona, the Mediterranean microplastic types are mostly polyethylene which was detected at 54.5%, polypropylene with 16.5% concentration, and finally polystyrene with also a considerable amount of 9.5%. Other types were also detected in respectful amounts along the coasts. Few of these abundant types of microplastics found were nylon polymers, polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC). The microplastic particles found in the Mediterranean Sea had a dominating shape and size, considering several samples from several locations (de Haan et al., 2019). The particles detected had a round shape, and of small size, around 1 millimeter, and with a light weight. The indication of this specific shape and weight is mainly related to their deterioration capacity, which was found out to be very advanced. This means that these types of microplastics are able to persist in the water for longer periods than the usual ones. Even though researchers have not yet precisely calculated the estimated time for microplastics before they get deteriorated in water, or buried in the seafloor, the danger they form on the marine environment is immense.

Effects of Microplastics on Human Health and Environment

An important question arises when talking about microplastics in water, which is regarding the final destination of these pollutants. However, this question is difficult to answer, as the microplastics behave differently depending on several factors. Some of the major factors are the granulometric size and shape of the particles, the physical and the chemical composition of the microplastics, and the environmental conditions of the water. What is of major concern to researchers is the effect of microplastics on the marine environment, on the living organisms in these environments, and more importantly, on human health.

Upon the increase of the quantity of microplastics in seas and rivers, the bioavailability of these particles for the organisms living in these environments also increases (Auta et al., 2017). This availability also depends on the characteristics of these microplastics. Marine biota is in danger of the ingestion of these small particles, as they mistaken them for food (Lonnstedt and Eklov, 2016). This may lead to many physical problems, such as the attachment of the plastic polymers to the internal parts of the animals which might lead to death. Other problems are also chemical such as inflammations and hindering the growth.

Another fact worth mentioning is the ability of microplastics to carry organic pollutants. Microplastic particles have high surface area and the great Van der Waals' forces lead to the high adsorption of organic pollutants from the water to the surfaces of the microplastics. The hydrophobic surfaces of microplastics have high attraction to organic pollutants which also aids the adsorption of the pollutants chemically as well (Teuten et al., 2009). The low density of some of the microplastics allows them to stay close to the surface of water, where their concentration thus increases. At the surface, the organic pollutants also persist, which allows microplastics to attach to and transport these pollutants with it, though the ability to do so depends on the polymers that form these microplastics. This upsurges the dangers that microplastics form on the marine environment.

The danger that microplastics can cause reaches out to humans as well. Some sea products are used as food products by humans, are their composition is affected by the presence of microplastics in the seawater. One obvious example is the sea salt. A study done by Yang et al. in 2015 has been done to detect the existence of amounts of microplastics in several international salt brands. The results have shown amounts varying between 7 and 681 particles per kg of microplastics in several different types of salt (sea salt, rock salt and lake salt). Several types of microplastics were detected in these salt products,

including polyethylene and cellophane. It is ironic, yet very sad, that the main causes of pollution of the seas with microplastics are various human activities, and the effects of these at some point reach out to humans as well.

Methods for Microplastics Removal from Water

The possible extent of removal of microplastics from water and wastewater mainly depends on the size of microplastics present. A study done in Europe proved that the ability of wastewater treatment plants to remove microplastics can reach between 90 to 99%. However, this percentage is lower for small-sized microplastics, varying from 20 to 300 μm (Browne et al., 2011). A more recent study, also in Europe, has shown that a wastewater treatment plant can remove 98% of microplastics (Murphy et al., 2016). Yet, the remaining amount of microplastics in the discharged water is still around 0.25 mp/L. These amounts thrown into fresh waters can accumulate and lead to dangerous unwanted levels of microplastics in water.

Internationally used plants for removal of microplastics and plastics from water and wastewater are wastewater treatment plants. The influent to these plants is the wastewater from industrial properties, commercial establishments and households. Several different processes can be used, some of which are physical, chemical and biological. The grouping of these processes in the plant leads to the removal of relatively large plastic particles from the water, decreasing also the concentration of organic materials in the water. Some plants might also have reactors to treat the water using disk filters, to decrease amounts of some materials in the water (Magnusson and Norén, 2014).

A common form of wastewater treatment plants is similar to the one shown in the figure 4, as suggested by Carr et al. (2016). Before starting with these processes, treatment of the wastewater is done to remove large debris or plastic particles that might act as obstacles for the proceeding processes. This step can be done through coarse filtering, gravel elimination, and crushing of big parts. Following this, the wastewater can be transferred to the primary treatment units. These units aim to get rid of organic and inorganic objects that are suspended in the wastewater, through sedimentation and membrane filtration. 50 to 70 % of the solids can be removed during this step, along with removing the grease and oil (Pescod, 1992). The secondary step is complementary to the primary one as it aims to remove any residuals from step one. Processes that might be used are stimulated sludge, dripping filters, and rotating biological contactors. The final step is sometimes integrated to apply advanced treatment methods that remove dissolved organics, metals and solids.

Figure 4 Typical wastewater treatment plant processes (Carr et al., 2016)

Several other remediation methods can be used for water treatment, to remove microplastics. These methods include (Klein et al., 2018):

1. Filtration
2. Incineration
3. Advanced oxidations methods such as ozonation.

However, these methods utilize large amounts of energy and are very costly (Tofa et al., 2019). Furthermore, these reactions might produce unwanted by-products which is also a problem when these are formed with high amounts. From here arises the need for advanced technologies for the degradation of toxic microplastics from water. This study will develop and discuss the application of an innovative photocatalytic method for the degradation of toxic microplastics, specifically by utilizing the trapping method which is useful in the case of low-density particles such as polypropylene.

Chapter 2: Photocatalysis Technology

In the past decade, the demand for clean water sources has highly increased, mainly due to the development in population and urbanization (Anele et al., 2018). This led to an increased attention toward to the shortage of this irreplaceable source, and considering the rate of industrialization and population improvement, this shortage is expected to grow with time. The reason for this is the pollutants and contaminants that are thrown into water all over the world, and in specific, the Mediterranean Sea. This environmental risk forces us as humans to treat and reuse the existing water resources as they are of limited quantities. These facts drew great attention of researchers towards finding feasible methods for treatment of water and wastewater. Several different methods have been developed for the treatment of water and wastewater in the past few years. For instance, biological methods for treatment were invented to remove unwanted pollutants from wastewater (Johnson & Mehrvar, 2008). Yet, such methods might lead to the production of undesirable by-products, that might be pollutants as well (Ganzenko et al., 2014). Other methods such as chlorination are also non-viable owing it to their high working costs. For this reason, it is a must to develop innovative and environmentally friendly methods for water treatment, specifically from microplastics. This chapter will present a brief history on photocatalysis technique, then it will explain the principle and mechanism of the process. Moreover, the system required for photocatalysis will be presented along with the advantages of the method and the factors affecting the resulting degradation rates.

History

The question of whether light alone can start a chemical reaction was tackled by Giacomo Ciamician in the year 1901, and he found that it is possible. Ten years later, the term “Photocatalysis” appeared in scientific articles (Lacombe & Keller, 2012). Zinc Oxide (ZnO) was one of the first photocatalysts to be used in experiments such as reducing Ag^+ to Ag under when exposed to irradiation during the year 1924. Although photocatalysis was discovered in the early 1900’s, it was not used efficiently in scientific research since no real applications were found initially. In the beginning of the 1970’s, an oil crisis occurred when the Arab petroleum exporting countries decided to seize the oil supply due to political reasons. Moreover, world organizations increased pressure to seek renewable sources of energy due to the increasing rate of pollution on earth (Outlook, 2010). Those reasons motivated scientists to expand their research in photocatalysis since light was considered as a clean and cheap source of energy. In the year 1972, Akira Fujishima and his PhD supervisor Kenichi Honda discovered that exposing TiO_2 electrodes to UV light allows the decomposition of H_2O . After the early 1970’s and Fujishima’s

discovery, scientific research on the subject of photocatalysis increased and several experiments were published. In the 1980's, the discovery of TiO₂ nanoparticles emerged as a new effective photocatalyst and were used in several applications such as in construction materials (Hashimoto et al., 2005). Scientists and researchers continue to investigate the subject of photocatalysis and try to find more advanced photocatalysts with better properties such as a wider bandgap (Hashimoto et al., 2005).

Principle

Photocatalysis, as indicated in its name, is a process that utilizes light along with catalysis to allow or to facilitate the occurrence of a chemical reaction [28]. The part 'photo' means light, which indicates that in photocatalysis process, the reaction is usually driven by the presence of light. To fasten the chemical reaction, a catalyst is used, that by definition, does not get altered during the reaction. In photocatalysis, irradiation used can be either applied directly to the reactants, or indirectly, where the catalyst used is exposed to irradiation, which makes it more capable of lowering the activation energy of the main reaction (Chou et al., 2013). Several types of catalysts can be used, depending on the source of light used and on the main reactants' composition as well. The type of catalyst chosen also dictates the type of photocatalysis occurring.

It is possible to separate photocatalysts into two groups that are homogeneous and heterogeneous. The catalyst used in the homogenous process is mostly a transition metal such as iron and copper (Lee et al., 2016). The product of this process is the hydroxyl radicals, which are spawned under certain light and thermal settings. These hydroxyl radicals are the main factor that allows the decomposition of the toxins when they react with organic materials. On the other hand, heterogeneous catalysts, such as TiO₂ and ZnO, are known to be in a different phase than the reactants (Lee et al., 2016). These catalysts are preferred due to properties such as their empty conduction band along with a filled valence, ability to absorb light, and the features of transporting charges.

The main aspects of a semiconductor photocatalyst are (Chen et al., 2010):

1. Reacts when exposed to light (Photoactive).
2. Activated under visible or UV light.
3. Inert from a biological and chemical aspect.
4. Does not corrode when exposed to light.
5. Cheap and nontoxic.

Heterogeneous photocatalysts allow the degradation of organic pollutants that are present in water efficiently, and it is preferred on most cases over homogeneous catalysts due to easy implantation since it does not need very specific pressure and temperature conditions in order to operate. Moreover, it allows full mineralization without a need for waste disposal.

Photocatalysis has witnessed an increase in its popularity recently since it is being used in several areas from wastewater treatment to antibacterial activity (Chen et al., 2010). The low cost and environmentally friendly characteristics of this technology allowed it to gain its popularity and become a main research topic for pollutant degradation in water.

According to Zhu and Wang (2017), photocatalysis, as a broad name for the several reactions that may exist under this title, can be divided into four main phases, as shown below and presented in figure 5:

- 1- Generation of electron-hole pairs through absorption of the energy of light. This energy is represented through the number of photons received. It is important to note that the band gap energy of the photocatalyst used must be either equal to, or smaller than the energy of the used light (Hagen, 2006).
- 2- Splitting of excited charges.
- 3- Allocation of the electrons and holes onto the exterior of the photocatalysts: a considerable number of the electron-hole pairs reconnect. The initially collected energy, from a heat source, or light emission, is the dispersed due to this recombination (Gershon et al., 2015).
- 4- The presence of hole allows the formation of the hydroxyl radicals, which in turn act as oxidizing agents. On the other hand, the electrons form the superoxide ions. Charges at the surface are now capable of aiding the occurrence of redox reactions.

Figure 5 Photocatalysis Principle (Zhu & Wang, 2017)

Mechanism

The equations that govern the explained concept of photocatalysis can be expressed in a general way. For the heterogeneous photocatalysis which employs semiconductors, that are metal oxides, a specific mechanism has been proposed for a very similar molecule to polypropylene, which is polyethylene and is shown in figure 6 (Tofa et al., 2019):

Norrish type I

Norrish type II

Figure 6 Mechanism for polyethylene degradation

System

Photocatalysis has proved itself to be a very effective and efficient method for protection and remediation of the environment. One of the sectors where photocatalysis can be utilized is water and wastewater treatment, where this method presents important potential and great efficiency. It employs sunlight for the removal of microplastics, organic pollutants and damaging bacteria, along with the help of solid photocatalysts (Tanveer & Guyer, 2013). It is worth mentioning that in addition to the type of photocatalyst used, the irradiation source also plays an important role in the efficiency of the treatment. As the strength of the irradiation is enhanced, the efficiency of the reaction increases (Fageria et al., 2014). For the sake of using the safest, cheapest and abundant source of irradiation for photolysis reactions, sunlight is the best candidate for this purpose. According to Balachandran et al. (2014), the energy magnitude given to the Earth by the sun, per year, is four times greater than that used by all humans annually.

For the reactions where sunlight will be utilized, a specific type of catalysts is preferable, one which can be activated by visible light. The photocatalyst to be used has to possess specific characteristics that make the system cost efficient, effective and fast. One of the most popular photocatalysts is the TiO_2 , as it is highly cost effective, nontoxic, very stable, and highly efficient. The mechanism by which the photocatalysis system works to degrade the pollutants from water can be considered a simple one. The job of the metal oxide in general is to absorb the ultra-violet light, or a light near this range, where the energy of the absorbed light causes the separation of charge, that finally leads to the formation of electron-hole pairs. At last, the electron-hole pairs allow the redox reactions to occur, with appropriate substrates (Devi & Kavitha, 2013). Yet, this photocatalyst still has some disadvantages, and these mainly are its low ability to absorb the light it is exposed to. Thus, to make it possible to use sunlight for the activation of these reactions while using TiO_2 , many advancements have been developed, such as doping of non-transition or transition metal, sensitization, ion implantation, and several others.

Advantages

Over the past decade, photocatalysis technology has been an attention-grabbing topic for the field of research. Especially as a water treatment technology, photocatalysis possesses great advantages over other treatment techniques, which makes it stand out as one of the most favorable water treatment technologies such as reverse osmosis, filtration, and incineration. When talking about photocatalysis as

a treatment technique, it is essential to understand what makes it more attractive than other traditional technologies:

- 1- The ability to utilize sunlight as a main energy for this technology renders it a renewable and non-polluting treatment technique.
- 2- Photocatalysis incurs very low costs with respect to other techniques that serve the same purpose.
- 3- Products that result from this process are harmless ones such as CO₂ and H₂O, opposing to other techniques which might produce unwanted products that need proper disposal.
- 4- Mild reaction circumstances, with a very acceptable reaction time.
- 5- Very low amount of waste products result from this process.
- 6- This technology can be applied to a wide range of pollutants with different characteristics and of several sizes.

Factors Affecting Photodegradation Rate

There exist several detailed factors that can affect the rate of the process of photocatalysis, both positively and negatively (Rajeshwar et al., 2008). Optimization of these parameters is essential to reach the best degradation result, in the shortest time possible. The major factors are listed and explained below.

- 1- **Size and surface of contact:** metal oxides as photocatalysts can be used either as bulk, relatively large-sized materials, or as nanostructured material. The advantage of the nanostructures, which are small-sized materials, is that they possess a large surface area allowing more contact with the pollutant dissolved in water. The small size of the catalyst is essential for the building of atoms over its surface. This in turn boosts the degradation efficiency of the catalyst (Han et al., 2014). Not to forget that the oxidation and reduction reactions occur at the surface of the catalyst, thus as the surface area is higher, more redox reactions occur.
- 2- **Mass of catalyst used:** increasing the amount of catalyst used means that the active sites' number is enlarged as well. This leads to the formation of a larger quantity of hydroxyl radicals HO^{*} and superoxide radicals O₂^{*-} (Rajeshwar et al., 2008). Until reaching an optimum amount of catalyst, increasing the amount thus enhances the degradation rate. However, after this optimal concentration is reached, any increase in the quantity of catalyst used will negatively affect the photodegradation. This is mainly because the catalyst would render it hard for the light to pass through it to reach the solution and the pollutant.

3- **Intensity of light:** depending on the bandgap of each metal oxide, a suitable range of wavelength exists where this specific catalyst functions the best. Taking TiO₂ as an example, which has a large bandgap equal to 3.2 eV, it mostly takes in the UV range of light (Reza et al., 2015). However, for ZnO which possess a low bandgap energy, visible light range is more suitable.

4- **pH of solution:** this factor is an important one as the charges at the surface of the photocatalyst and the pollutant differ as the pH of the solution changes. Considering the ZnO as the photocatalyst, its contact with water will lead to the formation of zinc hydroxide. The zinc hydroxide in turn is able to react either with H⁺ ions in an acidic medium, or with OH⁻ ions in a basic medium. The reactions that govern this process are (Degen & Kosec, 2000):

For low pH values, zinc hydroxide takes the protons onto its surface, rendering it to have a positive charge. On the other hand, for high pH values, the zinc hydroxide tends to lose protons from its surface, which leads to the formation of negative charges at its surface (Reed, 1986). It has been shown in previous studies that the ‘zero-point charge’ for ZnO is 9. With this in mind, one cannot indicate a perfect pH to be used in the presence of ZnO, since the pollutant is also affected by the pH of the solution. Thus, to optimize the pH of the solution for most efficient photodegradation, the pollutant’s reaction to the pH must be also taken into consideration.

5- **Amount of pollutant:** the time required for complete degradation of the pollutant in water highly depends on the amount of this pollutant dispersed in water (Han et al., 2014). It has been proved that at low concentrations of the pollutant in water, the photodegradation rate is higher, and complete mineralization, when possible, is achieved faster (Kiriakidou et al., 1999).

Chapter 3: Photocatalytic Degradation of Polypropylene by ZnO Nanorods

Following the literature study that has been done, application of photocatalysis process ought to be done at a lab scale. After that, the results need to be checked, verified, and finally compared to what was expected to be reached, as seen in the literature. Several preparations need to be done at the lab such as photocatalyst preparation, after which the photocatalysis set-up has to be placed. This chapter will show in detail how the preparations at the lab were done, presenting the calculations done and the equipment that were used. It will also include the photocatalysis set-up details, the sampling procedure and the characterization techniques used.

A- ZnO Nanorods on Glass Fiber Substrate

Since the invention of the photocatalysis process for degradation of pollutants in water, several photocatalysts have been introduced. For the purpose of our research, where heterogeneous photocatalysis is employed through the use of the energy of natural sunlight, semiconductor metal oxides are best used as photocatalysts. Among the metal oxides that exist in the literature and in the industry for photocatalysis, ZnO has been chosen, because of the several advantages that it possesses over other similar ones:

- Chemical and thermal stability
- Bandgap 3.37 eV
- Great exciton binding energy equal to 60 meV
- Non-toxicity
- Low cost and abundance
- Great mobility of electrons
- High oxidation-reduction potential
- Can be easily synthesized

It is essential to mention that the chosen metal oxide ZnO will be used at a nanoscale, in the form of nanorods built through hydrothermal growth on glass fiber substrate. This is important as it adds specifications to the photocatalyst such as a high surface-to-volume ratio and great ability for oxygen desorption. More importantly, glass fiber allows the use of trapping technique which serves as a solution to the problem of low density of polymers such as polypropylene. This increases the contact between the catalyst and the pollutant, thus increasing the photodegradation rate, making ZnO nanorods on glass fibers a perfect candidate to be used for the purpose of this research.

B- Preparation of Photocatalyst

The preparation of the photocatalyst requires preparation of solutions to be used for both the seeding of the ZnO layer and the growth of the ZnO nanorods. During the experimental work, the procedure was first done on glass substrates for the purpose of getting introduced to the type of work that has to be done. After that, for the purpose of this research the procedure was applied on fiberglass substrate, with the needed changes in the solution volumes and procedure. This part of the chapter will present the preparations done in the lab to obtain optimized ZnO nanorods on fiberglass substrates using seeding by spray, followed by hydrothermal growth. The process of synthesis of ZnO nanorods using hydrothermal growth is documented by Ullah & Dutta (2008).

1. Solution Preparation

Three main solutions were prepared following the optimized concentrations reported by Dutta et al., one for seeding and two others for hydrothermal growth (Ullah & Dutta, 2008). Considering the importance of the effect the pH of solutions on the photocatalytic degradation, the pH of each solution prepared was monitored before and after its use.

- **Zinc acetate dihydrate solution $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$:** zinc acetate powder with 97% purity and molecular weight $\text{MW}=219.5 \text{ g/mol}$ was used to prepare a solution of concentration $C=10 \text{ mM}$ and volume $V=100 \text{ ml}$ to be used for seeding by spray onto fiberglass substrate. The mass of powder needed was calculated based on the volume and concentration requirements, and was then mixed with a volume of 100 ml of distilled water to obtain the wanted solution:

$$m = MW \times C \times V = 219.5 \times 10 \times 100 \times 10^{-6} = 0.2195 \text{ g}$$

- **Zinc nitrate hexahydrate solution $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$:** zinc nitrate hexahydrate powder having 98% purity with a molecular weight $\text{MW}=297.46 \text{ g/mol}$ was used in order to prepare a solution of concentration $C=10 \text{ mM}$ and volume $V=300 \text{ ml}$ to be used in parallel with another solution for the hydrothermal growth of ZnO nanorods on fiber glass. The mass of powder needed was calculated as follows, and then mixed with 300 ml distilled water to get the solution required:

$$m = MW \times C \times V = 297.46 \times 10 \times 300 \times 10^{-6} = 0.89238 \text{ g}$$

- **Hexamethylenetetramine solution C₆H₁₂N₄**: the powder with 99% purity and molecular weight MW=140.19 g/mol was used to prepare the solution having a concentration of C=10 mM and a volume of V=300 ml. This solution, having a concentration equivalent to the zinc nitrate hexahydrate solution, was used also for the hydrothermal growth procedure. The mass for the powder required is also calculated according to the concentration and volume of the solution, as mentioned by Dutta et al., and finally mixed with a volume of 300 ml of distilled water to obtain the solution:

$$m = MW \times C \times V = 140.19 \times 10 \times 300 \times 10^{-6} = 0.42057 \text{ g}$$

The glassware used for the preparation of these solutions included simple material such as volumetric flasks of several different capacities and beakers of various volumes. A balance and a spatula were also used to weigh the powders used.

2. *Seeding of ZnO on Different Substrates*

The previously prepared zinc acetate dihydrate solution of concentration equal to 10 mM was used to form a seed ZnO layer onto glass slide substrate first for the purpose of training, then on fiberglass substrate for the purpose of this research. Fiberglass has been chosen as the substrate for this research due to the high surface to volume ratio it possesses as compared to a glass slide. The thread-like structure of fiberglass allows the ZnO to form countless nanorods on each and every thread of the fiberglass. Compared to the glass slide, this means multiplying the nanorods' number by a very large value, while keeping a constant volume occupied by the substrate.

Figure 8 shows a sample of the spraying process that has been done, however, on glass substrates, using the spraying device shown in figure 7. For the glass substrates, with a size 7.5 x 2.5 cm, the seed was done on one side of the glass slides. The glass slides were first prepared by being cleaned, using soap, acetone to remove all traces of soap left, and finally washed thoroughly by distilled water. Then, the glass slides were preheated in the oven at 90°C for around 30 min (Baruah & Dutta, 2009). This was done to prevent breaking of the glass slides when placed on the heating plate at 350°C. Using the prepared solution of zinc acetate with concentration of 10 mM and a volume of 25 ml, the glass substrates which were placed on the heating plate were then sprayed using the spray device, at a distance of around 15 cm and a rate of 1ml/min. Metal objects were placed on both ends of the glass slides to assure their horizontal positioning on the heating plate. After the spray process is done, the glass substrates are left for 30 min on the heating plate at the same temperature, to ensure the consolidation of the seeded layer.

Figure 7 Device used for spray

Figure 8 Spray procedure on glass substrates

As for the seeding on fiberglass, precautions had to be taken as this material is highly volatile and can cause itchy skin and great danger to the lungs if inhaled. For this reason, whole body parts were covered while working with the fiberglass, in addition to a full-head mask allowing no particles to be inhaled by mistake. First, the fiberglass was placed on a heating plate at a temperature of 350°C where the solution $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ was sprayed onto it at a rate of approximately 1 ml/min and from a distance around 15 cm, using the spraying device. After having sprayed an amount of 20 ml of the solution onto the first side of the fiberglass layer, the same procedure is repeated on the other side. In order to ensure the consolidation of the seed ZnO layer onto the fiberglass, the substrate is left on the heating plate at 350°C for around an hour. According to a study done by Baruah and Dutta (2009), when using zinc acetate for the seeding process, the morphology, crystallization and the direction of the nanorods formed depends on the post annealing temperature, which is the temperature that the substrate is left at to ensure the consolidation of the seed (Baruah & Dutta, 2009).. They have reported that at temperatures below 350°C , the directions at which the nanorods grew are formed in a very scattered manner, while mainly being perpendicular to the substrate surface. Meanwhile, the perfect temperature to obtain vertically aligned nanorods is 350°C , which is now known to be the optimum post annealing temperature to be used (Baruah & Dutta, 2009).

3. *Hydrothermal Growth of ZnO Nanorods*

After the seeding of the ZnO layer onto the fiberglass substrate, the substrate was placed in a chemical bath for hydrothermal growth of the ZnO nanorods. The solution used was a mixture of the two prepared equimolar solutions: zinc nitrate hexahydrate and hexamethylenetetramine. A volume of 250 ml of each solution was used. The optimal time for growth of ZnO nanorods onto fiberglass substrate is 65 hours in the oven at a temperature of 90°C. At the end of this step, the substrate is removed from the solution, and

Figure 10 Furnace used for heat treatment

Figure 9 Oven used for growth synthesis

washed properly with distilled water to physically remove all the ZnO material that has not been stuck on the fiberglass and has not been formed into nanorods. The fiberglass is then placed on a ceramic plate in the furnace for heat treatment at 350°C for 1 hour. As mentioned before, the best temperature for post-synthesis consolidation of ZnO is 350°C, allowing the annealing of the ZnO nanorods being perfectly aligned. The furnace is then turned off and the fiberglass remains in it till the furnace is cool enough in order to remove them. The oven and the furnace used are shown in the figure 9 and 10 respectively.

C- Photocatalytic Set-up

Photocatalytic degradation of polypropylene was done at lab scale for 17 consecutive days (including daytime and nighttime), which sums up to 196 hours under sunlight. As mentioned before there are several factors that affect the photodegradation of pollutants in water. It is essential to report all the initial conditions and values related to the pollutant and the light intensity as well, to analyze the results accordingly. This section will report the pollutant conditions and the light intensity under which photodegradation occurred.

1. *Pollutant: Polypropylene*

As already mentioned in the literature review, the amount of polypropylene in the Mediterranean Sea sums up to around 16% of all the plastic pollutants there. When talking about plastic items made of polypropylene, a recent study has found that the density of plastic in the Mediterranean Sea is around 1 item per 4 m² at the surface of the sea [43]. Being the 2nd most abundant microplastics' type in the Mediterranean Sea, polypropylene is a very thought-provoking topic for the field of research. This is because the ability to degrade it into non-toxic molecules such as CO₂ and H₂O will have a huge impact in decreasing the pollution in the Mediterranean Sea. For the purpose of this research, commercially available polypropylene with particle size 300 μm was used. A sample of the particles used is shown in the picture in figure 11.

Figure 11 Polypropylene (300 μm)

2. *Application of Photocatalysis at Lab Scale*

The target of this research is to study the degradation of microplastics under sunlight, in water and in the presence of a specific photocatalyst. In order to apply the photocatalysis process at a lab scale, a pyrex petri dish was used, where all the required reagents were placed. The prepared photocatalyst consisting

Figure 13 Photocatalysis set-up

Figure 12 Microplastics and photocatalyst in water under sunlight

of ZnO nanorods grown on fiberglass substrate was first placed in the dish. Then, a mass of 0.026 g of polypropylene particles with size 300 μm were placed and inserted as much as possible in between the fiberglass threads and below the fiberglass layer. It is vital to note that this has to be done without affecting the grown ZnO layer on the substrate, that is causing no lesion or incision to it. Placing the particles this way is done to prevent the microplastics from floating on the water surface when the distilled water is added. Then, a minimal level of distilled water is added to the dish, allowing almost all the placed microplastics to be dipped in water and at the same time in contact with the substrate. The dish was then covered with the best fit glass cover available, to avoid evaporation of water over the long exposure to sunlight. The level of water placed was marked from the outside to continuously ensure that no large amount of water has evaporated. As shown in figure 13, the covered dish was finally placed on the roof at the Faculty of Engineering at the Lebanese University, for 17 consecutive full days. A close picture of the fiberglass along with the microplastics placed in distilled water in the dish, before being covered is also shown in figure 12.

3. Sunlight Intensity Analysis

The use of sunlight as an energy source is one of the best innovations in the field of research so far. This is because it is a renewable source of energy that is cost free, which makes it the best candidate as compared to other sources of energy that have high costs and are not renewable. As mentioned before, this research simulates the use of sunlight for photocatalytic processes that aim to degrade microplastics in water. Usually, halogen lamps can be used for simulating sunlight as they are the closest ones to the black-body radiation spectrum of sun, and safest and easiest to use with respect to the effect of the light on eyes. At our lab in the Lebanese University, the halogen lamp was used for the purpose of other

researches for degradation of toxic molecules in water as well. However, for the research in hand, sunlight was chosen as the light source, to study the efficiency of the real sunlight on degradation of polypropylene, since for a large-scale application, sunlight will be used. Considering the fact that the month of July is one of the hottest months in Lebanon, it comes at our convenience to utilize sunlight during this month for the purpose of degrading microplastics in the sea. Thus, it was essential to check the sun intensity along different times of the day, to know when the samples should be taken and to be able to monitor how much light the process is receiving. The sun intensity, as perceived by the eye, can be measured in terms of the unit lux. The lux is an SI unit used to express illuminance, that is a measure of the luminous flux per m^2 . One lux is equivalent to one lumen per m^2 . The device used for measuring the lux is known as the lux meter, shown in figure 14. The lux meter uses a photocell to intake the light received. It then changes this into an electrical current, which allows it to calculate the lux accordingly.

Figure 14 Sun intensity vs time

Figure 15 Lux meter

The graph in figure 15 shows the change of the sun intensity, in lux, as a function of time. This graph represents a normal day during the month of July in Beirut, where the experiment of photocatalysis was done for 17 consecutive days. Since at this time of the year in Beirut, the sunrise time is around 6:00 a.m., and the sunset time is around 7:45 p.m., it was acceptable to consider that the time where the sun intensity is efficient for photocatalysis is between 7 a.m. and 7 p.m., which equals to 12 hours of sunlight per day. As can be seen in the graph, the sun intensity increases gradually from a minimum of 45,000 lux, till it reaches its peak at around 12:30 p.m., where the sun intensity is around 100,000 lux, which is more than double the minimum value. After mid-day time, the sun intensity decreases again progressively to reach around 50,000 lux by 7 p.m. Knowing these values helps decide the sampling time and more importantly helps analyze the results accordingly.

D- Characterization Techniques

In order to evaluate the quality of the work that has been done in the lab, several ways can be used as characterization methods. These characterization techniques can be such as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), which in the case of our research gives us a clear image of the zinc oxide nanorods that we have built. Moreover, to assess the extent of degradation of polypropylene with time, the Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy machine will be employed through the Attenuated Total Reflectance technique (FTIR-ATR).

1. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) is a type of electron microscope that produces several types of signals at the surface of the scanned object when exposed to a high-energy electron beam (Golstein et al., 2017). The SEM process reveals several traits about the sample such as the chemical composition and the texture of the material. Moreover, the SEM also reveals the crystalline structure, which is the special distribution of the atoms and molecules (Golstein et al., 2017).

The scanning process consists of selecting a certain two-dimensional area with a width ranging from 5 microns to 1 centimeter. In some cases, it is possible to perform a SEM on a point located on the surface of the material in order to determine properties such as the chemical composition or crystal structure (Golstein et al., 2017).

Figure 16 shows the setup of the scanning electron microscope. The electron gun at the top of the setup produces the electron beam that is received by the anode below. After that, the beam continues towards the first magnetic condenser lens that converges the beam initially and is responsible for modifying the resolution. The second lens, which is known as the objective lens, converges the beam again and focuses it towards the scanned sample. The scanning coil's role is to raster the electron beam on the studied sample (Golstein et al., 2017).

Figure 16 Scanning Electron Microscope setup (Golstein et al., 2017).

Figure 17 presents the scanning electron microscopy image of the ZnO nanorods grown on a glass fiber substrate, fabricated by Prof. Wael Hamd during his visit to KTH in Sweden. The procedure done for the seeding and growth of the ZnO nanorods on the glass fiber substrate is the exact one done in the experimental work of this research at the Lebanese University. After his visit, Prof. Wael Hamd reported that the ZnO nanorods resulting from seeding by spray appeared to be perfectly aligned, which means they had a very well distribution on the glass fibers. This guarantees that the followed method is an optimized one, and the ZnO nanorods grown on glass fiber substrate which was done for the purpose of this report would result in a very similar SEM image.

Figure 17 SEM image of ZnO nanorods on glass fiber substrate (Done in KTH by Prof. Wael Hamd)

2. FTIR-ATR: Attenuated Total Reflectance

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) is a technique used in order to find an infrared spectrum of absorption for materials of different phases (Griffiths & Hasseth, 2007). The working principle of most FTIR machines is shown in figure 19. The source shown in figure 19 emits a radiation that moves into the sample through the interferometer. Then, the radiation reaches the detector. At this stage, an amplifier is preset in order to amplify the signal and then using an analog to digital converter, it is fed to the computer. The data arrives to the computer in the time domain. Using Fourier transforms, the computer transforms the given data into the frequency domain in order for it to be analyzed.

Figure 19 FTIR working principle (Griffiths & Hasseth, 2007)

Figure 18 FTIR-ATR at Chemistry laboratory of Lebanese American University

Regarding the ATR mode in specific, which was employed in this research, several advantages over others make it stand out as the best technique to be used for characterization of solid polymers. The ability to test these particles very easily, while causing no damage to the particles is a great deal when it comes to these applications. Not to forget that the results we get are accurate.

The ATR machine used for the purpose of this research was available at the chemistry laboratory of the Lebanese American University and was employed with the cooperation of Dr. Robin Taleb. The machine used is supplied by the company Bruker, of type Alpha II-Platinum ATR, shown in the figure 18.

E- Alterations in Chemical Properties of Polypropylene

The most famous method used for studying the degradation of polymers is the FTIR spectroscopy technique. The FTIR-ATR technique, in specific, is distinguished by giving practical results without the need to destroy the tested samples, as well as being an easy-to-apply and non-time-consuming method. Although the results it gives are indirect, yet they can be very indicative of the extent of oxidation of the polymer in hand, which is polypropylene in our case. The concept is basically dependent on the different wavenumbers of light that the polymer can absorb, which in turn depends on the functional groups constituting this compound. Figure 20 shows the characteristic spectrum in FTIR-ATR of polypropylene used in this research before exposure to sunlight. As can be seen, several boldly vibrated peaks appear, each indicating a specific functional group of the polymer. C-H stretch can be observed in the range between absorbance values 2838 cm^{-1} and 2950 cm^{-1} . Methylene group CH_2 symmetric stretching vibration in specific can be detected by the peak of absorbance 2870 cm^{-1} . It can also be seen that the CH_3 rocking deformations exhibit strong vibrations at values below 1166 cm^{-1} , while the CH_2 rocking band appears below 840 cm^{-1} . Moreover, the CH_2 and CH_3 bends appear respectively at 1455 cm^{-1} and 1377 cm^{-1} .

Figure 20 FTIR absorbance spectra for pure polypropylene before photodegradation

Throughout the process of photocatalysis, the chemical constitution of polypropylene is altered. This results in rendering the molecules more and more inelastic, as their time under sunlight increases. This change in the chemical formulation of the polypropylene leads to the formation of new functional groups that were not present in the original sample. For instance, carbonyl, hydroxyl and esteric groups are

formed. For a clearer vision of the new groups formed, figure 21 shows a comparison between the peaks in the original pure polypropylene sample, and the final polypropylene sample after 196 hours of photodegradation. The graph proves the effect of ZnO catalyst in the oxidation of polypropylene. The evolution of the oxidation of polypropylene over time will be presented in what follows for a better understanding of the formation of new functional groups.

Figure 21 FTIR absorbance spectra for pure polypropylene and Oxidized polypropylene

The way to properly analyze the evolution of the chemical constitution of the polymers in hand, samples at several separate times were taken from the photocatalysis set-up and studied using the FTIR-ATR spectroscopy. Figure 22 presents the absorbances resulting from the five samples taken at different times during photocatalysis. The first sample to show first traces of change was taken after 69 hours of the start of photocatalysis. Remarkable results have been then seen from the results of the samples after 117, 154 and finally 196 hours. The squares on the figure represent focus areas that prove the chemical transformation in polypropylene, through the formation of new functional groups. The creation of the polar groups esteric, ketones and carboxylic acid proves the occurrence of the oxidation at the surface of the microplastics.

Figure 23 shows the first focus area, in which the carbonyl group appears in the range between 1700 cm^{-1} to 1780 cm^{-1} . The carbonyl group stretching mode that exists within this range results from aldehyde, ketone and anhydride groups. Aldehyde is responsible for the peak at 1738 cm^{-1} , and ketone for absorbance at 1719 cm^{-1} (Ali, S. et al. 2017). One can consider that the peaks are fairly clear, and mostly appear after 196 hours under sunlight. First there were no peaks for the appearance of aldehyde and ketone groups, which then started to appear after 117 hours of exposure.

Figure 22 FTIR absorbance spectra of polypropylene during photodegradation for 196 hours

Figure 23 Carbonyl group FTIR absorbance spectra (at 1735 cm^{-1})

The second focus area is mainly around a value of absorbance equal to 3400 cm^{-1} and is presented in figure 24. The peak in this region corresponds to the stretching mode of the OH group in alcohol. The consistently late appearance of the peaks representing the occurrence of oxidation can be mainly attributed to the fact that the size of the particles is relatively big, which allows only a small percentage of oxidation to occur at the surface of the particles. Yet, after 196 hours we can clearly spot the effects of oxidation in changing the chemical formation of polypropylene.

The third focus area is the one around absorbance value 1164 cm^{-1} , shown in figure 25. This value is a critical one, since as mentioned before, around this value the peaks for the C-H bend, CH_3 rocking and C-C stretch appear at a value very close to this one, this explains the presence of a peak in the

polypropylene pure sample. However, as reported by Abdouss et al. (1999), a peak at absorbance value 1164 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the presence of esteric groups in polypropylene after oxidation. This explains the consistent presence of this peak in the rest of the samples even after 196 hours of photodegradation.

Figure 24 OH group FTIR absorbance spectra in PP

Figure 25 Esteric group, C-H bend, CH_3 rocking and C-C stretch FTIR spectra in PP

It has been also noted in literature that unsaturated carbon bonds form upon the oxidation of polymers (Ali, S. et al. 2017). In our case, the formation of $\text{C}=\text{C}$ was recognized by the slightly appearing peak at 868 cm^{-1} as shown in figure 26. The shy appearance of this peak can be attributed to the fact that these bonds require more time to form than the bonds of C with O and H with O.

Figure 26 C=C FTIR absorbance peaks in PP

Table 2 summarizes the generate functional groups as a result of the oxidation of polypropylene after 196 hours under sunlight.

Table 2 Summary of functional groups generated after photooxidation

Functional Group	Vibration type	Strength	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)
Hydroxyl (-OH)	Stretching	Strong	3400
Aldehyde (C=O)	Stretching	Medium Strong	1738
Ketone (C=O)	Stretching	Medium	1719
Unsaturated (C=C)	Out of plane deformation	Variable	868

F- Carbonyl Index Analysis

The Carbonyl Index (CI) is a ratio used in order to quantify the degree of photodegradation of certain materials. Mathematically, the Carbonyl Index in the case of Polypropylene particles is considered to be the ratio of maximum carbonyl band over the reference band. In the following case, the reference band will be set as the CH₃ rocking band which is present at an absorbance of 972 cm⁻¹. As mentioned before in the analysis of the pure polypropylene sample, the peak at 972 cm⁻¹ is a clear one which renders it a good reference for calculating the CI (Mylläri et al., 2015).

The Carbonyl Index for Polypropylene is: $CI = \frac{Abs(1713\text{ cm}^{-1})}{Abs(972\text{ cm}^{-1})}$

The evolution of the CI with photooxidation time was generated in the graph in figure 27, by using the FTIR absorbance results of the samples that were taken at different times. The first observation that can be seen is that the carbonyl index increases exponentially with the increase in the degradation time. In the presence of a photocatalyst, polypropylene in water can be disintegrated when exposed to sunlight. This is a result of absorbance of some light waves, where the molecules of polypropylene get activated, and weathering begins to occur due to the existence of oxygen in the surrounding.

To verify the quality of the photodegradation of polypropylene, the increase in the CI value between original PP and final state has to be viewed. The value of the CI for pure PP was calculated to be 0.038. this value is an indicator of the existence of inherent chromophore of the polypropylene pure sample. The percentage of increase of the carbonyl index between time 0 hours till the first sample taken (after 24 hours) is calculated to be 13.16%. The second increment of increase, which occurs between the first sample at 24 hours, and the second sample taken after 69 hours, results with an increase of 151.2% of CI. Since the curve is an exponential one, the slope after this point decreases again gradually, with the third incremental increase in CI being 89.8%. Finally, at the region where the slope gets really smaller, the percentage of increase in CI is only 8.3%. The huge increase in the CI value at the beginning of the experiment, that is at times between 24 and 69 hours, is mainly due to the fact that the oxidation occurs at the surface of the particles which is easily accessible at the beginning. After surface degradation has already occurred, the rate of oxidation decreases since it is not easy to reach the inner part of the particles after the surface has already been oxidized.

Figure 27 Carbonyl Index change over degradation time

Finally, one can notice that the final CI value is around 6 times higher than the original one, which shows a relatively great degradation rate, considering the large size of the particles in hand, and the short degradation time spent under sunlight.

G- Method Limitations

It is vital to note that the normal research cases generate some errors for several reasons ranging from the exact way the absorbance was measured, to errors in sampling and preparation. In this case, baseline corrections could have been made to get more accurate CI values, as the baseline might change during photodegradation (Mylläri et al., 2015). It has also been proven in literature that the FTIR spectroscopy method can be a bit insensitive to carbonyl products when studying degradation times less than 40 hours (Rouillon et al., 2016). The results are more reliable at times higher than this value.

Conclusion and Perspectives

The fact that microplastics are of a very tiny size and are considered to be persistent when disposed in the environment is very alarming. The danger these particles form is human health is lethal, not to forget the species of marine and land animals that could die to microplastics' presence. For these reasons, researchers are looking up and developing degradation methods to eliminate these particles from water. This research was done at the Lab of Petroleum, Energy and Environment (PEE) at the Faculty of Engineering at the Lebanese University and serves as part of the contribution of the university to the project CLAIM, where the main goal is elimination of microplastics from water.

This work focuses on the analysis and development of the heterogenous photocatalysis process for degradation of polypropylene through the use of ZnO nanorods grown on glass fibers. Not only does it serve as an environmentally friendly photocatalyst, the use of glass fibers as substrates allows the use of trapping technology, which presents a solution to the problem of low density of microplastics. By utilizing the trapping technique, microplastics cannot float and can be trapped and degraded by using sunlight. The ZnO synthesis was first done glass substrate to assure the quality of the organic molecule used. Then it was applied to a glass fiber substrate where the degradation was then done and studied over time. The quality of the nanorods was assured to be very practical, where the SEM results showed perfectly aligned nanorods with good distribution. After applying the photocatalysis process for 196 hours, the results were to be analyzed using the FTIR-ATR spectroscopy. The machine utilized was at the Chemistry Laboratory at the Lebanese American University and was used with the help of Dr. Robin Taleb. The results showed the appearance of new peaks due to the oxidation of polypropylene and formation of new functional groups: carbonyl groups where detected in the range of absorbances between 1700 cm^{-1} to 1780 cm^{-1} , unsaturated carbon bonds (C=O) were seen by the change in the peaks at absorbance value 868 cm^{-1} , and finally OH stretching peaks were created, and they appeared by the peaks at 3400 cm^{-1} . The calculation of the carbonyl index resulted in an exponential increase of the CI over degradation time. The final degradation time CI (after 196 hours) resulted to be 6 times greater than the original one.

For further continuation of this research, several different sources of light can be employed to optimize the technique. Moreover, this technique can be applied to larger sizes of microplastics to check the extent of their degradation. The degradation rates resulted can be improved by modification of the ZnO nanorods to increase the kinetics of the degradation.

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